

Detention monitor

Tell us how you are doing

Help us gain insight into prison life

Help to give others a voice

- This questionnaire takes (**about**) **30 minutes** and is about victimisation.
- **Benefits of participation:**
 - I can share my experiences confidentially. Sometimes this leads to new insights.
 - This research is new in Flanders. It can contribute to a greater awareness of life in prison.
- **Discomforts of participation:**
 - Feeling uncomfortable with some of the questions asked and/or others in the prison can see that I am participating in the study.
 - The researchers cannot control how others (such as the media) understand the results.
 - The researchers treat everything confidentially, but in the case of theft, they have no control over it.
- Participation is **voluntary**. I can stop at any time.
- Participation is **confidential**. My name will never be published or passed on.
- If I stop, KU Leuven can **still use the previously collected data**.
- (Personal) data which is considered exceptionally **sensitive** under the General Data Protection Regulation is collected (**also gender, age, nationality, ...**).
- The results of this research can be used for academic purposes and may be published or be **publicly disclosed in a generalised way**.
- If I have any questions and/or wish to exercise my rights (inspection of data, correction of data,...) I can contact **Elien Goossens** (see contact details below).
- This research has been approved by the Social and Societal Ethics Committee. I or my family/friends can contact the Committee via smec@kuleuven.be with any additional questions or complaints.

If you consent, please tick every box.

YES

I have read and understood the above information. I have received answers to all my questions.

I understand what is expected of me and that I am participating in a questionnaire on victimisation.

I understand that my participation is voluntary. I have the right to stop participating at any time without having to provide any reasons.

I agree to take part and I consent to my answers being used.

Contact details

Elien Goossens

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How to fill in the questionnaire?

- **Check one box only** to indicate the situation most applicable to you.
- Provide a **single answer to each question, unless otherwise indicated**.
- The questions always refer to incidents **between inmates (not between inmates and staff)**.
- You must complete the questions **in full**.
- On the **last page** you can write more about your answers or the questionnaire. Those answers will not be used any further.
- Inside the **envelope** you will find **contact details of the service in this prison** you can contact if you have any concerns or uncomfortable feelings.
- When you have finished filling in the questionnaire, you can put it in the **closed envelope**. This will keep your answers confidential.

How to check an answer:

NEVER	ON 1-2 OCCASIONS	ON 3-5 OCCASIONS	ON 6 OCCASIONS OR MORE
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

How to correct an incorrect answer:

NEVER	ON 1-2 OCCASIONS	ON 3-5 OCCASIONS	ON 6 OCCASIONS OR MORE
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for your time and participation!

Part 1. Background

These questions are about your background. We will treat this **CONFIDENTIALLY**.

1. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Other

2. What year were you born?

Please complete using four numbers (for example, 1985):

3. What is the nationality on your passport? More than one answer may apply.

- Belgian
- Dutch
- Moroccan
- Turkish
- Italian
- French
- Russian
- Serbian/Yugoslav
- Romanian
- Spanish
- Polish
- Other (*please complete*):
- I don't know

4. Regardless of what your passport says, how do you feel most about yourself? Please choose one answer here.

- Belgian
- Dutch
- Moroccan
- Turkish
- Italian
- French
- Russian
- Serbian/Yugoslav
- Romanian
- Spanish
- Polish
- Other (*please complete*):

5. Do you have a legal residence permit for Belgium / Is your stay in Belgium legal?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

6. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- No diploma or certificate of completion
- Primary school
- Lower secondary education (year 1 to year 3)
- Higher secondary education (year 4 to year 6)
- Bachelor (this is university of applied sciences)
- University (this is an academic bachelor or master)
- Another Belgian education. Please give a short explanation:

.....

.....

.....

- Another foreign education. Please give a short explanation:

.....

.....

.....

- I don't know

7. To what extent do the following statements apply to you? It is about everything you have experienced or witnessed during your youth (0-18 years), in your family or environment.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE
There was a lot of physical violence during my youth.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There was a lot of emotional violence during my youth.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There was a lot of sexual violence during my youth.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Part 2. Feelings of insecurity

The questions below are about concerns in the last two months in this prison. If you have been in this prison for less than two months, please provide answers for the period since you arrived.

8. In this prison and during the past two months, have you been concerned that a fellow inmate was going to attack you? For example: hitting, threatening, stealing, ...

- Yes
 No —————> Please go straight to question 11 (on the next page).

9. In this prison and during the past two months, how often have you been concerned that one or more of the following situations might occur?

	NEVER	ON 1-2 OCCASIONS	ON 3-5 OCCASIONS	ON 6 OCCASIONS OR MORE
I was concerned that a fellow inmate would attack me or start a fight.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I was concerned that a fellow inmate would force me to take part in unwanted sexual acts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I was concerned that a fellow inmate would destroy or steal my things.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I was concerned that a fellow inmate would threaten, insult or otherwise emotionally hurt me.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

10. On the last occasion, how concerned did you feel when you thought that a fellow inmate was going to attack you?

- Not very concerned
 A little bit concerned
 Quite concerned
 Very concerned
 I don't know

Part 3 is about everything you have seen here. Part 4 is about your property during the last two months in this prison. If you have been in this prison for less than two months, please provide answers for the period since you arrived.

Part 3. The experiences of your fellow inmates

11. In this prison and during the past two months, how often have you seen the following incidents? This is about situations between inmates (NOT: staff).

	NEVER	ON 1-2 OCCASIONS	ON 3-5 OCCASIONS	ON 6 OCCASIONS OR MORE
I saw a fellow inmate performing unwanted sexual acts with another.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I saw a fellow inmate threatening, insulting or in any other way emotionally hurting another.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I saw a fellow inmate attack another or I saw a fight happening.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I saw a fellow inmate steal or destroy another person's things.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Part 4. Personal possessions

12. In this prison and during the past two months, how often have you experienced the following incidents?

	NEVER	ON 1-2 OCCASIONS	ON 3-5 OCCASIONS	ON 6 OCCASIONS OR MORE
A fellow inmate put pressure on me to give away my personal belongings, medication or other items, or I did so in return for protection.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate stole my personal belongings, medication or other items while I was <u>not</u> there.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate lied to me, causing me to lose my personal belongings, medication or other items.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate destroyed my personal belongings, medication or other items.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate stole my personal belongings, medication or other items while I was there.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Part 5. Emotional wellbeing

These questions are about offensive statements or behaviour in the last two months. If you have been in this prison for less than two months, please provide answers for the period since you arrived.

13. In this prison and during the past two months, how often have you experienced the following incidents?

	NEVER	ON 1-2 OCCASIONS	ON 3-5 OCCASIONS	ON 6 OCCASIONS OR MORE
A fellow inmate pretended to be my friend and took advantage of this.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate threatened me, frightened me or tried to do so.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate insulted me, mocked me, humiliated me or spread gossip about me.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate put pressure on me to make me do something I did not want to do, or I did so in return for protection.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate excluded me, ignored me and/or encouraged others to turn against me.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate made me angry, challenged me or tried to do so.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate lied about me to the staff to get me into trouble.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Part 6. Physical wellbeing

This is the second last part, which is about your physical wellbeing during the last two months. If you have been in this prison for less than two months, please provide answers for the period since you arrived.

14. In this prison and during the past two months, how often have you experienced the following incidents?

	NEVER	ON 1-2 OCCASIONS	ON 3-5 OCCASIONS	ON 6 OCCASIONS OR MORE
A fellow inmate made sexual comments, jokes or notes that made me feel uncomfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate attacked me <u>without</u> a weapon or object.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate put pressure on me to perform sexual acts, or I did so in return for protection.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate held me against my will or restrained me, locked me up or tried to do so.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate exposed their body or genitals against my wishes, or forced me to watch nude images.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate looked at me or whistled at me in a way that made me feel uncomfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate attacked me <u>with</u> a weapon or object.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate raped me (orally, anally or vaginally).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A fellow inmate touched me in a way that made me feel uncomfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Part 7. Detention situation

The last questions are about your detention history and your stay in this prison. Everything is treated **CONFIDENTIALLY**.

15. How many times did you stay in prison as an adult (18+), including the current detention? (Do not count transfers or revocations after a release)

Please complete in numbers: times

16. How long have you been in this prison without interruption? (Do not include transfers or revocations after a release)

- Less than 1 month
- More than 1 to 3 months
- More than 3 to 6 months
- More than 6 to 12 months
- More than 1 to 2 years
- More than 2 to 3 years
- More than 3 to 5 years
- More than 5 to 10 years
- More than 10 to 15 years
- More than 15 to 20 years
- More than 20 to 30 years
- More than 30 years
- I don't know

17. How long have you been in a prison without interruption? (This also includes the time you spent in another prison)

- Less than 1 month
- More than 1 to 3 months
- More than 3 to 6 months
- More than 6 to 12 months
- More than 1 to 2 years
- More than 2 to 3 years
- More than 3 to 5 years
- More than 5 to 10 years
- More than 10 to 15 years
- More than 15 to 20 years
- More than 20 to 30 years
- More than 30 years
- I don't know

18. Which of the three statements below apply to you? More than one answer may apply.

- In the past two months in this prison, I have used drugs.
- In the past two months in this prison, I have sold drugs.
- In the past two months in this prison, I have not used or sold drugs.

19. For each statement below, please let us know how often you have done so during the past two months in this prison.

	NEVER	ON 1-2 OCCASIONS	ON 3-5 OCCASIONS	ON 6 OCCASIONS OR MORE
I have sold items, food or protection to fellow inmates.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have had items and/or substances that are prohibited in this prison in my possession	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have disobeyed the staff.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have destroyed or stolen items from fellow inmates.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have shouted and sworn at fellow inmates, insulted or threatened them, excluded them or otherwise behaved in a hurtful manner towards them.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have attacked fellow inmates or started a fight with them.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have performed unwanted sexual acts on fellow inmates or pressured them into having sex.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

20. In this prison during the past two months, you generally participated in...

	YES	NO
... leisure activities outside the cell (sports, creativity, ...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
... the library	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
... work (kitchen, laundry, workhouse, ...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
... education and/or training outside the cell (language-, vocational training, ...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
... the walks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
... religious and moral assistance (the imam, pastor, priest, chaplain, moral counsellor, ...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

21. Think back to what happened more than two months ago in this prison. To what extent do the following statements apply to you?

If you have not been in this prison for more than two months, choose N/A (not applicable).

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	N/A
Fellow inmates destroyed or stole my property more often than that of others.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fellow inmates threatened or insulted me more than they did to others.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I was more than others the target of physical violence by fellow inmates.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I was more than others the target of sexual violence by fellow inmates.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

22. What do you think your first response would be if a fellow inmate were to attack you (cause a fight, steal from you, shout and swear at you, ...)?

- I would wait until the incident has passed
- I would seek help from staff (report the incident, ask for a transfer etc.)
- I would seek help from fellow inmates
- I would talk to the offender(s), negotiate with them, make a deal etc.
- I would run away, hide or flee
- I would scare off the offender(s) (by threatening them, for example)
- I would fight back or shout and swear back
- Other (*please complete*):

23. What is your current detention situation? More than one answer may apply.

- In custody awaiting trial or not yet convicted
- Convicted
- Awaiting the outcome of an appeal or cassation
- Revocation after release (suspension, postponement, electronic surveillance, conditional release)
- I don't know

24. For which of the following offences that you are currently in prison for are you convicted or under suspicion? More than one answer may apply.

- Traffic-related offences
- Property offences without violence (for example: theft/stealing, fraud, forgery, vandalism, ...)
- Property offences with violence (for example: extortion, violent robbery, ...)
- Violent offences (for example: assault, battery, murder, involuntary manslaughter, ...)
- Drug-related offences (for example: possession, sale or growing of drugs, ...)
- Sexual offences (for example: indecent assault, voyeurism, rape, ...)
- Terrorism offences
- Other (*please complete*):

25. Are you currently staying in a section with an open or closed regime?

- Open
- Closed
- I don't know

26. Are you currently staying in a special unit or do you have a special regime? For example, a drug-free unit, a deradicalisation unit, safety regime

- Yes. *Please let us know which type of unit or regime:*
- No
- I don't know

27. Are you currently sharing a cell with other people?

- Yes. *Please indicate in numbers how many people you are sharing a cell with:*
- No

